

3D PRINTING OF RECYCLED PET POLYMER COMPOSITE INFUSED WITH SUSTAINABLE CARBON

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this work is to develop a novel low cost and sustainable biochar/recycled Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) composite with improved mechanical and thermal performance. The biochar was derived from pyrolysis of packaging waste at a high temperature and autogenic pressure. The typical temperature and pressure of the reaction are ~ 1100 °C and 150 bar. The biochar was ground and sieved to below 100 μm , and it was melt compounded with recycled polyethylene terephthalate derived from post-consumer PET bottles (Aquafina®). Biochar/PET composite filaments of 1.75 mm were produced using a melt extruder. The filaments were used to 3D print a tensile, DMA, and TMA sample coupons using Hyrel 30M printer. The biochar was analyzed for its textural properties, thermal stability, and surface morphology using XRD, Raman spectroscopy and field emission scan electronic microscopy FESEM. The surface morphology was examined using field emission scan electronic microscopy (FE-SEM). The surface area measurements were carried out using Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) experiments. XRD results show that the as prepared carbon is crystalline with slight amorphous background. The as-prepared polymer composite was studied for their thermal, mechanical and dynamic mechanical properties. These results showed that the incorporation of the biochar improved the composite mechanical, thermal and dynamic properties. A 0.5 wt% of biochar infusion in PET resulted in 32% increase in tensile strength. The polymer composite with 5 wt% loading has shown 60% increase in tensile modulus over the neat PET. Moreover, the biochar has significantly improved the composite dynamic modulus, dimensional stability and thermal stability in an oxidative environment.

1 INTRODUCTION

Three-dimensional (3D) printing is a manufacturing technology that consists of building parts by depositing the material through a nozzle on a layer by layer basis. Each layer of material is deposited using a heated thermoplastic filament or solution and pushed through a nozzle onto a substrate or heated bed based on computer aided design (CAD) model. Once one layer is finished, the bed is lowered down to build the next layer, and the process will continue until the full shape is built [1, 2]. It is one of the most promising and fast-growing technologies for fabrication of polymer composites[3]. For a long time, 3D printing was limited to rapid prototyping applications only. Nowadays, there is a trend for using 3D printing in the fabrication of actual parts such as parts for automotive industry. 3D printed parts have mechanical properties comparable to parts produced by conventional techniques such as extrusion and compression molding. However, both starting material and printing parameters should be carefully selected to meet performance requirements of specific applications.

Packaging waste is a huge environmental problem, which needs immediate attention. Recent survey indicates that about one-third of all municipal trash is packaging waste. This waste can be recycled, or reused as a raw material for synthesis of value added products. In this research, we have studied the conversion of packaging waste materials into a highly porous activated carbon for polymer filler applications. Highly porous carbon was synthesized from waste packaging material (foam) mainly made of water-soluble starch and other biodegradable ingredients. We have carbonized this starch using thermal pyrolysis process in the presence and absence of the potassium hydroxide (KOH) chemical activation. This process was carried out in a batch reactor at high pressure and temperature (parr reactor) conditions.

Polyethylene terephthalate is the most used thermoplastic in beverage bottling, textile fibers and thin film applications [4]. It comprised 62.5 % of the US plastic bottles market with 6172 million pounds in 2016. A considerable amount of disposed PET finds its way to recycling with a recycling rate of 28.4% [5], [6]. During the processing of recycled PET small fraction of moisture, causes resin degradation (hydrolytic chain scission). Though water is the primary source of degradation [7]. Chain cleavage reduces intrinsic viscosity, and molecular weight leads to degradation of the mechanical properties. Comparing the properties of recycled and virgin PET resin, the virgin PET exhibited 200% elongation while recycled exhibited less than 10% elongation at break[7]. Recycle and reuse post-consumer PET has been thoroughly investigated in the literature. The approaches varied between mixing recycled resin with virgin resin at various ratios, blending with other polymer materials and the addition of fillers to produce materials with properties close or superior to the original material. Though PET has excellent mechanical and optical properties, its 3D printing has not been investigated in detail. Moreover, as a recycled PET is expected to have lower properties due to possible degradation during processing, incorporation of filler may improve recycled

PET performance to meet the requirements of engineering and automotive applications.

Biochar is a promising sustainable carbonaceous filler, defined by The International Biochar Initiative as a solid material obtained from the thermochemical conversion of biomass in an oxygen-limited environment[8]. The evolution of volatiles from feedstock during carbonization process results in loss of carbon from the solid phase. Carbonization in a closed system under autogenic pressure is known to improve the biochar yield and reduces the amount of volatiles released in the atmosphere. Moreover, high pressure allows graphitic sheets to grow, curl and reorganize bonds at relatively lower temperatures[9]. Biochar was extensively investigated as a material for soil remediation and soil amendment, heavy metals removal from water, carbon capture, electrode materials for supercapacitor, an anode for fuel cell and catalyst for syngas conversion. The utilization of biochar for the polymer filler applications are still not well developed. Recently, Das et al. published several articles about biochar potential to improve the properties of wood PP composites. The studies investigated biochar from different feedstock and synthesized at different conditions. The biochar composites have shown improved tensile/ flexural moduli and lower heat release under combustion regime [10]. In the second study on wood, polypropylene composite concluded that the addition of biochar reduced the composite flammability by restricting oxygen transfer into PP. It also improved the modulus and preserved the strength[11]. Lignin-based biochar introduced in Poly(trimethylene terephthalate) polymer increased heat deflection temperature by 90% in addition to improving the tensile and flexural moduli resulting in bio-based composite suitable for automotive applications [12]. The properties of PLA/PTT blend/ biochar have shown dependency on biochar particle size distribution. Biochar with particle

size range of (75-20 μm) resulted in an improved dispersion and improved energy dissipation. The resulting composite had an impact strength of 85 J/m which is high considering the brittle nature of the blend [13].

Polyethylene terephthalate has poor fire properties. B Xue, Niu, and Y Yang have recently published three articles on carbon microspheres made using the hydrothermal method and modified microspheres. They investigated its performance in improving PET thermal and fire properties. PET/Microencapsulated carbon microspheres (MCMSs) have improved the limiting oxygen index, and composite reached V-0 rating in UL-94 tests [14]. Magnesium hydroxide coated carbon microspheres, 1.0 wt% of $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ @CMSs resulted in LOI value of 27.5% and V-0 rating in UL94 [15]. Carbon microspheres with double shell layers of magnesium hydroxide and polyethylene terephthalate improved the fire performance index and smoke production rate while preserving mechanical properties [16].

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials: Peanut shaped loose filler packaging material (BRAN FOAM TOP), made primarily from starch, was purchased from ECOLOPACK (Japan). Aquafina® used water bottles were collected locally at Tuskegee University clean bins.

2.1 Methods.

2.2 Synthesis of autogenic biochar

Twenty-five grams of packaging waste was fed into Ni-based superalloy high-pressure/temperature reactor (GSL-1100X-RC). The reactor was heated using a temperature-controlled furnace. The waste was heated from ambient temperature to 1100 °C at a rate of 20 °C/min soaked for two hr at 1100 °C and under the autogenic pressure of ~150 MPa. Then the vertical reactor is allowed to cool down to ambient temperature. The resulting biochar was ground in a mortar and sieved to below 100 μm .

2.3 Textural properties

Biochar textural properties were investigated using NOVA2200e (Quantachrome, USA) surface area and pore size analyzer. All samples were vacuum degassed at 150 °C overnight to remove volatiles before further analysis is carried out. Nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms were obtained at 77 K and partial pressure range of (0.05-0.99), adsorption isotherms were further used for estimation of BET surface area, volume and pore size distribution. BET surface area was calculated using multi-point test in a partial pressure range of (0.05-0.3), micropore volume was estimated using Non-Linear Density Functional Theory (NDLFT). Total pore volume was measured at a partial pressure of 0.99.

2.4 Surface morphology and microstructure

The morphology and microstructure of biochar and were investigated using FE-SEM (Jeol JSM -7200F) and Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM-Jeol 2010). The fracture surface morphology of the composites were also investigated using The FE-SEM.

2.5 Composite fabrication.

PET bottles were shredded using conventional Power Smart electric shredder. Shredded plastic was dried in a desiccant dryer at 120 °C for four hours before further processing. Dried PET was mixed with packaging waste derived biochar at loadings of (0.5,1,3 and 5%) in Filabot extruder (with L/D ration of 24) at 250 °C and extruded into 1.75 mm filament which was further used for 3Dprinting. All test specimens were 3D printed using the Hyrel30M 3D printer (Ga, USA) equipped with MK450 hot head. The 3D models of test specimens were designed in Free Cad software and sliced using the Slic3r software. Infill type of rectilinear with 100% fill was used, and objects were printed with two perimeters. The rest of printing parameters were set in Slic3r software as follows: nozzle diameter 0.6 mm; layer height 0.40 mm; nozzle temperature 270 °C; bed temperature 50 °C. The printing speed was fixed at 50 mm/s. To prevent frequent nozzle clogging the retraction length was reduced to 0.4 mm while retraction speed was changed to 25 mm/ s.

3 Composite characterization

3.1 Mechanical properties

Tensile tests of PET and its polymer composites were carried out using Zwick Roell Z2.0 mechanical testing system. The test was carried out according to ISO 527 (ASTM?) standard. The tests were carried out at a crosshead speed of 10 mm/min of in 2.5 KN load cells with wedge grips. TestXpert data acquisition software was used to record the test data.

3.2 Differential scanning calorimetry

Differential Scanning calorimetry (DSC) A TA Q 2000, differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) was used to study thermal behavior of the recycled PET and its biochar composite. Samples of about (10-15) mg were sealed in an aluminum pan and heated from room temperature to 300 °C at a ramp of 5.0 °C/ min.

3.3 Thermogravimetric analysis(TGA)

Thermal properties: Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried out using TA Q 500 TGA. The samples were heated from room temperature to 700 °C at a heating rate of 5 °C/ min, under both nitrogen and oxygen environment.

3.4 Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA)

Viscoelastic properties of recycled PET and biochar/PET composites were obtained from the dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA). DMA tests were conducted according to ASTM D4065 standard using TA instrument DMA Q 800. The tests were performed in dual cantilever mode at a frequency of 1 Hz and temperature range of 30 °C and 150 °C using a heating rate of 5 °C/minute.

3.5 Thermo-Mechanical Analysis (TMA)

Thermo-mechanical analysis (TMA) was carried out to investigate the coefficient of linear thermal expansion CLTE using a TA Instrument Q400. The dimensional change was

measured in the thickness direction at a temperature range of 25 °C to 110 °C at a heating rate of 5 °C/ min and under the flow of nitrogen gas. The CLTE was calculated from the slope of TMA thermograms between 25 and 60°C.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

DMA is used to investigate the viscoelastic properties and relaxations associated with molecular motions in biochar/ PET composite. The viscoelastic properties of biochar/PET composite compared to the neat PET is presented. It can be clearly seen that the incorporation of biochar has changed the polymer viscoelastic properties. Since PET is viscoelastic materials, it can store and dissipate energy. The addition of biochar even at low loading of 0.5% has increased PET ability to store energy which is reflected in the increase of storage modulus. The storage modulus has increased by 18% from 1455.285 to 1715 MPa at biochar loading of 0.5%. The composite energy storage capabilities increased as the filler loading increased. The composite with 5% biochar has a storage modulus of 2062 MPa which represents 42% increase in storage modulus compared to neat PET indicating more elastic behavior. The increase of storage modulus demonstrates strong mechanical interlocking between biochar and PET which improves the composite stiffness. The ratio of loss modulus to storage modulus is often referred to as tan delta is represented in (fig 1-B).

Figure 1 Dynamic Mechanical Properties a) Storage Modulus b) Tan Delta

Tan delta is an excellent tool to quantify the energy dissipation in polymer composites. Generally, high values for tan delta corresponds to viscous behavior while low values demonstrate the elastic behavior. The value of tan delta varied between 0.72 for neat PEAT and 0.30 for the composite with 5% biochar loading. There is decreasing trend for tan delta as the amount of biochar is increased. The values of tan delta reflect the viscous behavior of neat PET and elastic behavior of the composite. The glass transition temperature can be obtained from DMA, the temperature at the apex of the tan delta. The peaks of composite samples are shifted to the right as biochar weight % is increased demonstrating an increase in glass transition temperature. As expected these results show higher glass transition temperature values than the DSC results. Moreover, the anisotropic nature of 3D printed samples dynamic may have led to this difference. The parts building parameters greatly affect elastic properties (storage modulus). Parameters such as layer height affect the bonding between adjacent layers

also the number of layers determine the temperature gradients in z-direction as the number of layers is increased for the same part thickness the temperature gradient increase[1].

4.2 Thermomechanical Analysis (TMA)

The coefficient of linear thermal expansion (CLTE) was calculated from TMA thermograms (fig 2.) below 60 °C. The CLTE of pure PET is 53.2 ppm/ °C which is lower than the literature reported values (60-80). All biochar/PET composite have CLTE lower than the neat PET in a range of (37.0-50.8) this reduction can be ascribed to the low CLTE of biochar filler. In particular, biochar loading of 1.0% resulted in 30% reduction in CLTE. The incorporation of biochar has enhanced the dimensional stability. Lower CLTE is known to minimize the thermal stress in 3D printed parts and prevents its deformation during the cooling process. These results suggest 3D printing of PET composite can be carried out at ambient temperature without heated bed and produces parts with excellent dimensional stability and minimum deformation due to thermal stress.

Figure 2 Composite Thermomechanical Analysis (TMA)

4.3 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The tensile properties of neat PET and biochar/PET composites are represented in (Fig .3). These results clearly show that the incorporation of biochar has improved the tensile strength and modulus. All the biochar/PET composites have shown better tensile strength compared to the neat PET. The PET/0.5wt% polymer composite has the highest (32%) strengths(51.87MPa) compared to the neat and other percentages of loading. The higher percentage loading of biochar has shown the decreased properties. This decreasing trend can be attributed to biochar agglomeration at higher loadings. The tensile modulus has increased with the biochar loading. PET-B-5wt% has the highest figure for tensile modulus of 0.88 GPa which is 60% higher than neat PET modulus. The improvement in mechanical properties can be attributed to the excellent mechanical properties of the filler and the good interfacial bonding between PET and the filler. These results show that the properties can be altered by loading of various percentage of biochar depending on the requirement.

Fig.3. Tensile Properties a) Stress strain curves b) Tensile Strength c) Tensile Modulus.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Recycled PET and PET /biochar composite were successfully extruded into 3D printable filaments. We were successfully able to 3D print parts out of 100% recycled PET. Biochar synthesized at high pressure and high temperature has excellent textural properties and graphitization degree. The incorporation of biochar has enhanced the mechanical thermal and dynamic properties of 3D printed parts and may serve as a potential alternative for commercial graphene materials in polymer composites. The biochar improved PET nucleation and improved the crystallinity. The novel properties biochar and its excellent bonding with PET has resulted in a composite with improved mechanical properties. The improvement in thermal properties can be attributed to the barrier effect of biochar. The composite has excellent dimensional stability leading dimensional accuracy and less thermal stress deformations in printed parts. Finally, waste materials are a sustainable abundant source for value-added 3D printing materials with improved properties.

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